

A photograph of a megalithic stone archway. The sun is shining brightly through the opening, creating a lens flare effect. The surrounding landscape is dark and silhouetted, with some trees visible in the background.

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On the cover: Markov Kamak Sanctuary in Rila Mountain. Photo by Vasil Markov.

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THE AZURRAGUE DOLMEN IN THE CONTEXT OF MEGALITHISM IN ALTO RIBATEJO

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Abstract. The article discusses the Dolmen of Azurrague 1 (also known as Zorrague), which is part of the MEDICE II project. It is located in the Vale do Azurrague, in the parish of Alburitel, Ourém. This archaeological site is significant for the study of megalithic monuments in the central region of Portugal characterized by limestone. The coexistence of funerary monuments with natural cavities contributes to a better understanding of the megalithic phenomenon. This study aims to provide a preliminary analysis to this archaeological site by exposing its characteristics, relevant contexts, and intra-site interpretations.

Keywords: dólmen, prehistory, megalithism

Introduction

The present article aims to provide an initial approach to the dolmen of Azurrague 1, hereafter referred to as Azurrague (Fig. 1), based on data collected during the archaeological campaign in July 2024, which is part of the MEDICE II project, approved by the Public Institute for Cultural Heritage.

Figure 1. Dolmen I of Azurrague

The archaeological site is located in the Vale do Azurrague, in the parish of Alburitel, municipality of Ourém, in central Portugal (Fig. 2). The study of megalithic monuments in the limestone region of central Portugal reveals features of great scientific relevance. The coexistence of megalithic funerary monuments with natural cavities, where contemporary rituals were performed, makes this area especially interesting for understanding the megalithic phenomenon. This dynamic necessitates a broader approach regarding the functionality and motivations that led to the adoption of these structures. The coexistence of traditional worship sites with ritual practices within these structures

raises pertinent questions. Did the same community groups use both spaces? Did these sites serve distinct purposes? What was the importance of these monuments for local communities and for foreign groups? What messages and meanings were being communicated through these practices? What rituals were common between both types of spaces, and what divergences or transformations were observed in the ritual behaviours?

Figure 2. Map of Portugal showing orthophoto map and north-south and west-east profiles of the Azurrague dolmen. Its location in a valley is visible. Source: Google Earth.

The investigation of the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta (Fig. 3), located in Alvaiázere in the north, has been central to addressing these questions (Figueiredo, 2007, 2010, 2013, 2017, 2021; Figueiredo et al., 2024). This study now extends to the megalithic monument of the Azurrague 1 dolmen, located in the municipality of

Vila Nova de Ourém, approximately 18 km southwest of Rego da Murta. In this region, only the Dolmens of Rego da Murta and Azurrague 1 are known, with the Azurrague 1 dolmen still in the early stages of excavation. However, there are references to possible locations of other megalithic monuments, although these remain imprecise and have not been archaeologically confirmed (Pereira, 2006; Figueiredo, 2007).

Figure 3. Alto Ribatejo map, highlight on the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta and Caves.

The dolmen of Azurrague 1, therefore, plays a significant role in the ongoing study of the megalithic phenomenon in the limestone region, particularly due to the diversity of forms and ritual practices associated with the coexistence of different cultural traditions. This multifaceted archaeological landscape challenges interpretations, requiring a more complex understanding of the cultural traditions that coexisted in the region (Oosterbeek & Cruz, 1997; Figueiredo, 2019a, 2021; Scarre & Oosterbeek, 2019; Cruz, 2020a). As the only known dolmen in Ourém, the dolmen of Azurrague 1 underscores the importance of further investigations to identify other similar sites and

highlights the need for more detailed studies to understand funerary and ritual practices.

The theoretical complexity arises from the need to articulate different symbolic and functional systems in an interpretation that considers the possible interactions and overlaps among various cultural traditions and the innovations adopted, as reflected in a range of ritual practices during recent prehistory. This is one of the central challenges of the MEDICE II project, which aims to explore these communities through archaeological interventions in natural cavities and megalithic monuments in the region. The project seeks to clarify perspectives on how these groups manipulated and attributed meanings to the sacred landscapes, thereby shaping collective expression and promoting the anthropization of these areas.

Figure 4. Prehistoric context near Azurrague I dolmen

The proximity of less than 2 km between the Anta do Azurrague 1 and the cave of Lapa da Furada (Fig. 4), which exhibits evidence of human occupation contemporaneous with the megalithic phenomenon in the region, renders this dolmen the closest site to a natural cavity

where analogous practices can be observed. Thus, it is unlikely that the communities performing such acts were unaware of the practices at the other location, suggesting that they were probably part of the same group.

This study may answer some detailed questions: What archaeological evidence might suggest or refute direct interactions between the two spaces? How might the choice of locations for conducting rituals relate to the accessibility of these areas? Could these locations have served complementary purposes, such as hosting different celebrations at distinct times in the ritual calendar? How might rituals in the cavities and megalithic monuments have served to reinforce social cohesion and collective identity, and how did this relate to neighbouring groups?

Brief archaeological and landscape context

The archaeological site sits within a narrow band of Upper Jurassic formations, composed of marls, sandstones, schists, limestones, and intercalations of marls and conglomerates (Fig. 5).

The site is situated within the Estremenho Limestone Massif (ELM), which lies between the Ourém basin and the Tagus basin (Manuppella et al., 2000). The ELM is characterized by sedimentary formations from the Middle and Upper Jurassic periods, primarily consisting of limestones, dolomites, marls, and arkoses (Fig. 5). From a geomorphological perspective, the area is part of the Azurrague Valley, itself within the Serra de Aire and the S. Mamede Plateau. Drainage in the vicinity of the Azurrague dolmen is provided by the Ribeira de Chão de Maças, which feeds into the Tagus basin. The Serra de Aire and S. Mamede Plateau is a vast region distinct from the coastal platform, reaching its highest elevation between the Mira de Aire and S. Mamede sites before gradually descending to the Ourém basin.

Within a radius of 5 km to the west lies the site of Buraco da Foz, a small cavity where human bones were also detected during the 2023 survey. Other significant prehistoric occupation sites are known only within a 9 km radius, particularly in the Agroal region, where a large concentration of remains from this period has been found (Lillios, 1989,

1991; Cruz, 1997; Zilhão, 1987; Oosterbeek, 1994). Major examples of megalithism in the region are represented by the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta to the north and the Anta do Vale da Laje to the east (Oosterbeek, 1994)—the latter having once belonged to a cluster of sites, the other members of which have now been destroyed. Nearby, on the opposite side of the Zêzere River, the cluster of Jogada and Vale Chão also stands out (Cruz, 2010).

Figure 5. Geologic map of Alto Ribatejo with principal sites

The Dolmen I of Azurrague

This is a chamber-and-corridor dolmen (Fig. 1). Architecturally, the chamber and the corridor are distinguished by the heights of their supports. Based on the work done so far, the corridor would have consisted of three lateral slabs. The difference in height between the remaining elements of the corridor and the chamber suggests that a respectful (perhaps even ritualistic) posture was required when entering.

The site has been significantly disturbed and structurally damaged. The first excavation campaign uncovered a set of lithic artifacts—including flakes and cores made of flint, some arrowheads and blades, undecorated ceramic fragments with open, spherical forms, a considerable number of polished tools, and two rectangular schist mica plates that were likely used for sharpening tools. Human bones and animal remains were also found.

Inside the chamber, a large number of macrolithic artifacts were recorded in the most recent deposits, which had already been greatly disturbed; these artifacts appear to be absent from the corridor area. Regarding the human remains, several poorly preserved bone fragments were excavated, including pieces of mandibles and maxillae as well as loose teeth—altogether representing at least six individuals, according to Silva's (1993) method. The anthropological analysis indicated that some bones exhibited signs of post-burial burning, likely resulting from taphonomic processes and/or human activities.

Faunal remains of rabbits, hares, and goats were also collected. The macrolithic artifacts consist of fragments of large flakes and cores worked in quartzite using ancient techniques, suggesting a continuity of cultural practices in the Alto Nabão region.

It is important to highlight several notable aspects—particularly the presence of macrolithic materials and a consistent deposition associated with the polishing of axes, adzes, and grinders, an occurrence that is not commonly observed.

At the time of writing this article, we had not yet received the results of absolute dating. However, based on the typology of the arrowheads and looped buttons, the site appears to fit within the transition from the 4th to the 3rd millennium, showing many similarities (including construction features) with the initial occupation of Dolmen I at Rego da Murta (Figueiredo, 2002, 2003a, 2003b, 2004a, 2004b, 2004c, 2004d, 2004e).

Particularities of some contexts observed during the excavations

One of the notable findings concerns the presence of macrolithic artifacts in the earliest excavated levels, which poses a significant challenge for understanding the continuity of cultural practices during recent prehistory. These lithic elements, made of quartzite, have been found at various sites, including those associated with megalithic monuments such as the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta (Figueiredo, 2004c, 2004d, 2004e, 2005), the dolmens of Zêzere—where cores from Jogada, Vale Chãos, and Vale Laje have been recovered (Oosterbeek, 1997; Cruz, 2010, 2020a, 2020b)—and at the Azurrague dolmen.

When comparing only the sites in the karstic area of Alto Nabão—which includes the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta and the Anta da Azurrague—we observed a significantly higher percentage (possibly over 200%) of lithic instruments at the latter. These remains are primarily concentrated in the earliest excavated layers and are found exclusively in the chamber area, a pattern also visible in the dolmens of Rego da Murta (Figueiredo, 2021, pp. 124–130). They consist of diverse cores for opportunistic knapping and rough quartzite flakes, a relatively common raw material in the river courses of the Nabão.

Observations in Portugal indicate that these artifacts have been knapped using essentially the same technique since the Paleolithic, often being attributed to—or considered very similar to—the so-called Languedoc industry (Raposo & Silva, 1984; Jorge, 1990; Grimaldi et al., 1998, 1999a, 1999b; Oosterbeek, 2004). This designation was initially introduced by Henri Breuil in the early twentieth century during his discoveries in the Garonne Valley near Toulouse (Jorge, 1990). Later, studies by Louis Méroc in the 1940s and 1950s established a more recent chronology for these materials, extending into the pre-Chassens Neolithic (Jorge, 1990). During that period, Zbyszewski observed artifacts with characteristics similar to those previously noted by Joaquim Fontes in Campos, in the province of Pontevedra near Minho (Jorge, 1990). Based on analogies and subsequent discoveries, these artifacts have been documented in various parts of Portugal, with particularly significant occurrences in the coastal Central region, along

the Tagus, in the Quaternary beaches of Minho, on the Alentejo coast (between Sines and Vila Nova de Milfontes), and along the Guadiana River (Breuil & Zbyszewski, 1942). They are also extremely common at sites near the Nabão River.

These artifact sets have been characterized by “degenerate coups de poing,” along with various shaped pebbles—such as “proto-Asturian points and Mirenses or related axes” (Jorge, 1990). In interpretive terms, the scientific community has regarded these materials as a “convergence phenomenon” (Jorge, 1990), meaning that they represent a technique for exploiting a macro quartzite toolset that was particularly practical and useful in Alto Ribatejo. This method allowed for effective flaking of an abundant and advantageous raw material, ensuring both economic profitability and simplicity in the production of functional artifacts (Cruz et al., 2000; Cura et al., 2004).

We prefer to avoid terms that might lead to limiting or misguided interpretations—such as “Languedoc”—opting instead for the simple designation of macrolithics.

In the archaeological context of the region under study, the use of macrolithics has persisted since at least the Upper Paleolithic, as evidenced by the Ribeira da Atalaia site (Oosterbeek & Cruz, 2003; Cruz et al., 2000), and extending into the Bronze Age at habitation sites such as Santa Margarida on the Tagus (Baptista, 2004), Maxial near the Zêzere (Cruz & Oosterbeek, 1998a, 1998b), and Castelo da Loureira in the valley of Nabão (Figueiredo et al., 2014), near the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta (Figueiredo, 2007, 2010, 2019a, 2021). These artifacts also occur in ritual deposits in caves (Zilhão, 1992; Oosterbeek, 1994; Figueiredo, 2019b) and in megalithic monuments near the Zêzere River to the east (Oosterbeek, 1994; Cruz, 1997, 2004; Gaspar & Batista, 2001) as well as along the Nabão (Figueiredo, 2002, 2003a, 2004a, 2005)—including the dolmen of Azurrague. This macro toolset almost always appears in association with a microlaminar and geometric industry, as well as with polished artifacts.

At the Dolmen of Azurrague I, we observed the same association. In particular, the discovery of a flint trapeze along with several axes and adzes made of amphibolite was noteworthy. Similar artifacts to those recorded in stratigraphic units 1 and 2 of the Dolmen

of Azurrague are also found in layers C and D of Anta I of Val da Laje (Oosterbeek, 1994), in the pits of Monument V of Jogada (recently designated as Pedra Encavalada (Cruz, 2010), at the Monument of Colos (Gaspar & Baptista, 2000, 2001), and in levels C and D of the Cadaval cave (Cruz, 2010). They further appear in levels 2 and 3 of various stratigraphic units dated to the mid-Copper Age at Dolmen II of Rego da Murta.

Outside the region, these artifacts are present in contexts associated with the Mesolithic/Neolithic tradition—for example, at the habitat of Pipas in Reguengos de Monsaraz, which may correspond to the early and middle phases of megalithism in Reguengos (Silva, 1987, p. 90).

A particularly noteworthy feature in the context where polished artifacts were found is their concentration near the first support of the corridor, on the right-side wall. In this specific case, six axes and adzes were collected alongside a mica-schist plate containing biotite. Another polished axe and a mica-schist plate with both biotite and muscovite were found within the chamber. Macroscopic analysis reveals a diversity of morphological types and varieties of amphibolites, linking them primarily to deposits in the south along the Tagus and Zêzere. Ongoing studies on samples of these amphibolites aim to confirm and provide clearer details about their origins.

Final considerations

The preliminary results of the excavation raise questions about the social and ritual dynamics of the peoples who inhabited this region during prehistoric periods, inviting a deeper reflection on the relationships between built and natural spaces. Continued research at Dolmen of Azurrague I will certainly contribute to enriching our understanding of megalithism in Portugal, offering new insights and narratives about the lives and practices of our ancestors.

The interpretative hypotheses regarding cultural persistence and the importance of macrolithic artifacts, as mentioned earlier, are reinforced by studies indicating a continuity of practices over various prehistoric periods. The association of these artifacts with both

habitation sites and megalithic monuments suggests they held functional as well as symbolic relevance—a topic also discussed in other archaeological works (Figueiredo, 2007; Cruz, 2010).

Furthermore, the issue of cultural persistence can be observed in other European contexts. For example, investigations at Mesolithic and Neolithic sites in southern France reveal that communities maintained stone knapping techniques from earlier periods, like those observed in the Languedoc artifacts from the Alto Nabão region. This points to a phenomenon of “technological convergence,” whereby certain techniques continued to be used due to their efficiency and symbolic value.

The megalithic structure, a chambered dolmen with a corridor, is representative of the typical monuments in the region. However, it is noteworthy for its unique proximity to a cavity with absolute dating that provides insight into the construction and occupation phases of these monumental structures.

Another point worth exploring, which underscores the significance of studying this monument, is the absence of other known sites in relatively good condition that would allow for further research in the region. Planned archaeological surveys may shed more light on this apparent isolation; for now, this dolmen remains unique in this regard.

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